

ON PAIRED SAMPLES T-TEST: APPLICATIONS, EXAMPLES AND LIMITATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The paired samples t-test is a commonly used statistical procedure for comparing the means of two paired populations to determine their equality. In this paper, the applications, examples and limitations of paired samples t-test are illustrated using real data employing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, a prominent software tool for the said test.

Keywords: *Paired samples t-test; two matched groups; paired populations; mean difference*

INTRODUCTION

In a mathematical approach to hypothesis tests, we start with a clearly defined set of hypotheses and choose the test with the best properties for those hypotheses. In practice, we often start with less precise hypotheses. For example, often a researcher wants to know which of two groups generally has the larger responses, and t-test could be acceptable (Fay & Proschan, 2010). A paired-samples t-test compares the mean of two matched groups of people or cases, or compares the mean of a single group, examined at two different points in time (Ross et al., 2017). It is one of the widely-used statistical procedures for comparing the equality of the means of the two paired populations. The basic underlying assumption of the test is that observations should meet certain preconditions, such as normality, equal variances and independence (Park et al.,

2020; Kim, 2015). Many researchers employ the paired t-test to evaluate the mean difference between matched data points (Hedberg & Ayes, 2015).

Research Objectives

This research study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To define paired samples t-test;
2. To provide readers with the use and practicability of paired samples t-test; and
3. To lay down the limitations of paired samples t-test.

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper was to examine the applications, examples, and limitations of the paired-samples t-test. The primary approach involved conducting a comprehensive literature review. Various sources, such as scholarly articles, textbooks, and online resources, were searched using specific keywords like "paired samples t-test" and "limitations of t-test" to find relevant information. Only sources that clearly explained the applications of the test, provide real-world examples, or discuss its limitations and assumptions were included. Studies that focused on alternative tests or lack a connection to the applications, examples, or limitations of the paired-samples t-test were excluded. The collected literature was analyzed to identify key themes regarding the t-test. Important points and relevant data will be recorded. Furthermore, the methodology incorporated illustrative examples to demonstrate the practical use of the paired-samples t-test in real-world scenarios. This approach aimed to establish a clear framework for exploring the usefulness of the paired-samples t-test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and discussions of the study.

Applications of paired samples t-test

The paired sample problem denotes situations in which two measurements are taken from the same object or individual to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the mean difference between paired observations is significantly different from zero (Grzegorzewski, 2022). The SPSS software is a very common statistical software in educational research that can be used to analyze the differences of a variable after being given treatment. One of the variables that can be analyzed is the difference in student learning outcomes. Teaching materials used in learning can cause differences in student learning outcomes (Afifah et al., 2022). Taking the Excel and SPSS analysis of the independent sample t test as an example, the inference analysis process of randomly designing two sample data is explained, and the actual analysis is solved by comparing the analysis results of the two processes in the experimental study. For the two independent sample t-tests, the data obtained by using the Excel tool is complete and

more accurate, but the operation is complicated. The SPSS tool is simple and convenient to operate, but the data is not accurate by Excel (Gao et al., 2018).

Examples of paired samples t-test

A group of Sports Science students ($n = 20$) are selected from the population to investigate whether a 12-week plyometric-training programme improves their standing long jump performance. In order to test whether this training improves performance, the students are tested for their long jump performance before they undertake a plyometric-training programme and then again at the end of the programme (i.e., the dependent variable is "standing long jump performance", and the two related groups are the standing long jump values "before" and "after" the 12-week plyometric-training programme) (Laerd Statistics, 2023).

Figure 1: Step 1 of the data analysis

Source: <https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/dependent-t-test-using-spss-statistics.php>

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You will be presented with the **Paired-Samples T Test** dialogue box, as shown below:

Figure 2: Step 2 of the data analysis

Source: <https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/dependent-t-test-using-spss-statistics.php>

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Transfer the variables **JUMP1** and **JUMP2** into the **Paired Variables:** box. There are two ways to do this: (a) click on both variables whilst holding down the shift key (which highlights them) and then pressing the button; or (b) drag-and-drop each variable separately into the boxes. If you are using older versions of SPSS Statistics, you will need to transfer the variables using the former method. You will end up with a screen similar to the one shown below:

Figure 3: Step 3 of the data analysis

Source: <https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/dependent-t-test-using-spss-statistics.php>

Note:

- button shifts the pair of variables you have highlighted down one level.
- button shifts the pair of variables you have highlighted up one level.
- button shifts the order of the variables within a variable pair.

- 4** If you need to change the confidence level limits or exclude cases, click on the **Options...** button. You will be presented with the **Paired-Samples T Test: Options** dialogue box, as shown below:

Figure 4: Step 4 of the data analysis

Source: <https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/dependent-t-test-using-spss-statistics.php>

- 5** Click on the **Continue** button. You will be returned to the **Paired-Samples T Test** dialogue box.

- 6** Click on the **OK** button.

Figure 5: Steps 5 and 6 of the data analysis

Source: <https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/dependent-t-test-using-spss-statistics.php>

Output of the Dependent T-Test in SPSS Statistics

SPSS Statistics generates three tables in the **Output Viewer** under the title "T-Test", but you only need to look at two tables: the **Paired Samples Statistics** table and the **Paired Samples Test** table. In addition, you will need to interpret the boxplots that you created to check for outliers and the output from the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality, which you used to determine whether the distribution of the differences in the dependent variable between the two related groups were approximately normally distributed. This is explained in our enhanced guide. However, in this "quick start" guide, we focus on the two main tables you need to understand if your data has met all the necessary assumptions:

Paired Sample Statistics Table

The first table, titled **Paired Samples Statistics**, is where SPSS Statistics has generated descriptive statistics for your variables. You could use the results here to describe the characteristics of the first and second jumps in your write-up.

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	JUMP1	2.4815	20	.16135	.03608
	JUMP2	2.5155	20	.15982	.03574

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Figure 6: Output of the paired samples t-test

Source: <https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/dependent-t-test-using-spss-statistics.php>

Paired Samples Test Table

The **Paired Samples Test** table is where the results of the dependent t-test are presented. A lot of information is presented here and it is important to remember that this information refers to the **differences** between the two jumps (the subtitle reads "Paired Differences"). As such, the columns of the table labelled "**Mean**", "**Std. Deviation**", "**Std. Error Mean**" and "**95% Confidence Interval of the Difference**" refer to the mean difference between the two jumps and the standard deviation, standard error and 95% confidence interval of this mean difference, respectively. The last three columns express the results of the dependent t-test, namely the *t*-value ("**t**"), the degrees of freedom ("**df**") and the significance level ("**Sig. (2-tailed)**").

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	JUMP1 - JUMP2	-.03400	.03185	.00712	-.04891	-.01909	-4.773	19	.000

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You are essentially conducting a [one-sample t-test](#) on the differences between the groups.

Reporting the Output of the Dependent T-Test

You might report the statistics in the following format: $t(\text{degrees of freedom}) = t\text{-value}$, $p = \text{significance level}$. In our case this would be: $t(19) = -4.773$, $p < 0.0005$. Due to the means of the two jumps and the direction of the *t*-value, we can conclude that there was a statistically significant improvement in jump distance following the plyometric-training programme from 2.48 ± 0.16 m to 2.52 ± 0.16 m ($p < 0.0005$); an improvement of 0.03 ± 0.03 m.

Figure 7: Paired samples t-test table and reporting the output

Source: <https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/dependent-t-test-using-spss-statistics.php>

Limitations of paired samples t-test

Some methodologists have cautioned against using the t-test when the sample size is extremely small, whereas others have suggested that using the t-test is feasible in such a case (De Winter, 2019). For designs that only involve factors with two levels each, the paired t test can be used for power calculations, but some pitfalls need to be avoided (Langenberg et al., 2023). For most non-parametric models, the Bahadur–Savage result yields that the size of the t-test is one for every sample size. Even if we restrict attention to the family of symmetric distributions supported on a fixed compact set, the t-test is not even uniformly asymptotically level α . However, the convergence of the rejection probability is established uniformly over a large family with a very weak uniform integrability type of condition. Furthermore, under such a restriction, the t-test possesses an asymptotic maximin optimality property (Romano, 2004).

There are at least six assumptions of paired samples t-test:

- 1) Your dependent variable should be measured on a continuous scale (i.e., it is measured at the interval or ratio level);
- 2) Your independent variable should consist of two categorical, "related groups" or "matched pairs";
- 3) There should be no significant outliers in the differences between the two related groups; and
- 4) The distribution of the differences in the dependent variable between the two related groups should be approximately normally distributed. If a violation to the assumption is not correctable, you will no longer be able to use a dependent t-test (Laerd Statistics, 2023).

Conclusions

Although the paired-samples t-test is a robust method for analyzing paired data, researchers should be aware of its limitations. Small sample sizes can affect the sensitivity of the test. Moreover, it may be necessary to explore alternative non-parametric tests when the normality assumptions are not satisfied.

In summary, the paired-samples t-test is an essential tool for researchers who want to evaluate mean differences in related samples. By recognizing its strengths and limitations, researchers can use this test to draw meaningful conclusions from their data and contribute to advancements in their fields.

Recommendations

This study provides valuable recommendations for researchers, data analysts, and educators regarding paired-samples t-tests. Researchers should carefully consider whether the paired t-test is suitable for their study design, particularly when working with related samples or pre-post intervention measurements. It is crucial to understand the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance. If these assumptions are violated,

alternative tests or data transformations may be necessary. Both researchers and readers should be aware that small sample sizes can affect the sensitivity of the test. Lastly, data analysts should clearly report the test statistic, degrees of freedom, and p-value to ensure proper interpretation of the results. Educators can utilize this knowledge to emphasize the paired-samples t-test as a fundamental tool for analyzing data from related samples, highlighting its applications, assumptions, and limitations. By following these recommendations, researchers, data analysts, and educators can ensure the effective use and understanding of this valuable statistical test.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors of this study assure that ethical procedures were strictly followed.

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